

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- The multi-country One Health EJP Simulation Exercise ([One Health EJP SimEx](#)) conducted in 2022 is an example of learning from experiences across sectors and countries.
- 10 European countries shared how beneficial the One Health EJP SimEx conduction was to their national response teams.
- The participating countries identified areas for future improvements in their outbreak response, including improved data sharing and enhanced communication across sectors.
- All countries identified a willingness to participate in future simulation exercises.

One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop Series: Joint SimEx/ Dissemination Workshop

A ONE HEALTH SIMULATION EXERCISE AS A ROADMAP FOR FUTURE FOODBORNE OUTBREAK PREPAREDNESS

The One Health EJP Joint SimEx/Dissemination Workshop 'A One Health Simulation Exercise as a roadmap for future foodborne outbreak preparedness', took place online on the 6th of December 2022. It was organised jointly by the SimEx Project Team of the Work Package 4 (WP4), and the Work Package 5 (WP5) Science to Policy Translation of the One Health EJP, as part of the Dissemination Workshop series. In addition to those who participated in the One Health EJP SimEx, the event targeted an audience with decisional power, including policy makers, decision makers and risk managers.

The presentations focused on the experiences from conducting the [One Health EJP SimEx](#) and applicability of One Health EJP-produced solutions to improve prevention, detection, and response to pathogens in One Health approach.

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...bridging across the sectors, sharing data, having a common understanding of health issues, and overall building trust and unity.

Welcome and Introduction to the One Health EJP SimEx

Annemarie Käsbohrer, leader of [Work Package 5 Science to Policy Translation](#), [BfR](#), Germany

Karin Artursson, leader of [Work Package 4 Joint Integrative Projects](#), [SVA](#), Sweden

Annemarie Käsbohrer and Karin Artursson greeted the participants and introduced them to the overarching aim of the [One Health EJP](#): enhancing collaboration and activities in the fields of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats. Paramount to achieving this aim is bridging across the sectors, sharing data, having a common understanding of health issues, and overall building trust and unity. The One Health EJP SimEx tested the capability, capacity and interoperability of actors in public health, animal health and food safety to work together.

One Health EJP SimEx background

Rebecca Litzell Forss, [One Health EJP SimEx Project Team](#), [SVA](#), Sweden

Rebecca Litzell Forss gave some background on the aim and organisation of the One Health EJP SimEx. The preparation of the One Health EJP SimEx started in 2021; it then went through a phase of design based on ECDC's handbook of simulation exercises in EU public health settings. It was conducted at national level as a 2-day exercise between May and September 2022, and was evaluated, both by the participating countries and by the One Health EJP SimEx Project Team. The SimEx had three focus areas: roles and functionality, harmonised data collection and data sharing, and communication. In total, 255 participants in 11 European countries took part in the exercise.

One Health EJP SimEx scenario

Mats Lindblad, [One Health EJP SimEx Project Team](#), [SLV](#), Sweden

Mats Lindblad gave an overview of the One Health EJP SimEx scenario. Briefly, the One Health EJP SimEx was a table-top exercise on a national level *Salmonella* Typhimurium outbreak that involved both the food chain and pet feed chain. *Salmonella* Typhimurium is a pathogen familiar to all participating countries, and a suitable choice for a One Health cross-sector outbreak involving Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety authorities.

The practical exercise foresaw the use of the [FoodChain Lab web application](#), a software that allows the visualisation and analysis of data...

The chosen source of infection was cattle. Although not the most common source for salmonellosis, this would involve the cooperation of many authorities relevant for both human food and raw pet feed industry and challenged the response protocols that countries may already have in place for poultry salmonellosis outbreaks. A scenario was set up, which included the need to share whole genome sequencing (WGS) data. The practical exercise foresaw the use of the [FoodChain Lab web application](#) (developed by the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) as a joint result of One Health EJP [COHESIVE](#), and [EFSA](#) projects), a software that allows the visualisation and analysis (importantly the trace back) of data needed for such an investigation.

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At the end of the exercise, each authority that took part discussed the lessons learned from the outbreak investigation, both what went well, and the identified gaps to be addressed to improve cross-sectoral coordination during a health crisis.

One Health EJP SimEx experiences across Europe

Pikka Jokelainen, deputy leader of [Work Package 5 Science to Policy Translation](#), and the [National Exercise Leader of Denmark, SSI, Denmark](#)

Pikka Jokelainen chaired a session in which ten countries (Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, France, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, and The Netherlands) shared their experiences with the One Health EJP SimEx, the identified needs, and the lessons learnt.

The experiences shared were positive and interesting to other countries.

The experiences shared were positive and interesting to other countries. Common issues identified included General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and data sharing challenges. In addition, data were reportedly often not optimally interoperable across the sectors. Besides technical aspects, transparent and early cross-sectoral communication was identified as being of paramount importance. A positive outcome of the One Health EJP SimEx mentioned by many countries was that it allowed participants to have a deeper understanding of the roles and mandates of the different actors across the sectors.

Evaluator's view of the One Health EJP SimEx

Charlotte Grastilleur, Local Evaluator, [ANSES, France](#)

Charlotte Grastilleur presented the conclusions of conduction of the One Health EJP SimEx in France, carried out at ANSES headquarters, from a local evaluator's view. The exercise demonstrated that all actors had a clear view of each other's missions at the national level but it was less clear regarding European or international agencies and structures.

The One Health EJP SimEx was an opportunity for participants to review their knowledge and procedures and to share experiences.

The One Health EJP SimEx was an opportunity for participants to review their knowledge and procedures and to share experiences. It reinforced the link between participants and strengthened the National Network for Crisis Management in feed/food safety. Next Generation Sequencing and genomics are being adopted as a universal standard, but questions about knowledge in the field have been raised and there are challenges around data sharing at a global scale. It was however agreed that the One Health approach is a key point in risk management to tackle zoonotic threats.

Food Chain Lab Web: An integrative software to visualise and analyse complex global food supply chain networks during foodborne incidents

Marion Gottschald, [BfR, Germany](#)

Marion Gottschald presented the FoodChain-Lab software - a tool used as part of the One Health EJP SimEx.

Globalised trade is characterised by long and complex supply chains, which are associated to increasingly complex risk assessments and outbreak investigation data, making it

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The future involves standardisation of tracing data to foster interoperability of, and data sharing between, tracing software solutions in Europe and thereby enhance crisis preparedness.

necessary to count on powerful integrative tools. FoodChain-Lab (FCL) is an open source software created for this purpose. It is available in a [desktop format](#) or as a [web application](#).

FCL allows the visualisation and analysis of complex supply chain networks consisting of food business operators and deliveries, with automated visualisation of the common source of the pathogen or contaminant and of the cases. Hereby, the sensitive tracing data always remain on the user side. FCL helps with the simulation of hypotheses, aiding to prioritise the next investigation steps. Internationally, it has been applied during several foodborne incidents in Member States and European level and it has been integrated into the Tripartite's SISOT toolbox. FCL is being continuously improved in close collaboration with EFSA. Support and training for FCL can be requested at foodrisklabs@bfr.bund.de. The future involves standardisation of tracing data to foster interoperability of, and data sharing between, tracing software solutions in Europe and thereby enhance crisis preparedness.

During the One Health EJP SimEx, participants used the FoodChain-Lab web application when analysing the *Salmonella* outbreak. Participants did not need to have previous experience of use of the software and found it interactive and easy to use.

One Health EJP Simex results

Frederico Alves, One Health EJP SimEx Exercise team, [SVA](#), Sweden

Frederico Alves presented a summary of the preliminary results of the One Health EJP SimEx.

The exercise involved participants from public health (37%), food safety (35%) and animal health (23%) sectors in 11 European countries.

With respect to roles and functionality, when focusing on collaboration, responsibilities, and on how to use guidelines and available tools, 88% of the participants reported an improved knowledge on their own and other sectors in the event of a zoonotic outbreak.

The recommendations put forward were to create One Health strategies, guidelines and procedures at institutional level...

The recommendations put forward were to create One Health strategies, guidelines and procedures at institutional level; to hold regular meetings and training sessions with authorities from all sectors; to improve coordination between regional and central authorities; to implement official communication channels between institutes; to harmonise typing methods and to reinforce inter-laboratory networks.

On data sharing, focusing on understanding the benefits of a One Health perspective during a zoonotic outbreak, 90% of participants reported to have increased their understanding on the importance of data harmonisation practices. Importantly, 18% felt their home institute did not prioritise data harmonisation practices.

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Among the gaps identified were lack of political will, cost, time, and a need for training in data analysis (especially regarding Whole Genome Sequencing). Lack of data sharing methodologies and a need for a common data platform, as well as lack of GDPR legislation, were also identified as major gaps. Consequently, the recommendations put forward were to strengthen the links between human and veterinary primary health care practitioners and the reference laboratories, to implement common data collection and data sharing platforms, and to provide training in genomic data analysis and interpretation.

Regarding communications, 92% of participants reported an increased understanding of the different communication needs for target audiences. As major gaps, they identified the lack of a well-structured communication plan, and lack of integration of the communication team in the response team.

The conduction of the One Health EJP SimEx was well received by the participants who overwhelmingly (94%) reported that they felt encouraged to pursue a One Health approach and to work closely with other sectors in a future outbreak situation.

The experiences from One Health EJP SimEx will be useful for planning future One Health simulation exercises. The positive experiences of both the organisers and the participants are encouraging.

Recommendations for future One Health simulation exercises

On exercise logistics, it was recommended to hold preparatory meetings prior to conduction of a simulation exercise, to divide the responsibilities of conduction between the facilitators from different sectors, and to incorporate more operational and practical tasks in the exercise. With regards to One Health, it was recommended to identify and group countries with similar systems for the scenario chosen, to consider including more sectors (e.g., environmental sector), to have a stronger focus on communication strategies, and to evaluate the level of One Health-ness before and after the exercise.

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